

The Effect of COVID-19 on the Socio-Economic Status of the Jordanian Workforce: Learned Lessons and Suggested Solutions

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Abstract

COVID-19 has impacted all facets of life in Jordan and worldwide, which created real crises especially for the workforce. The crisis hit hard causing unemployment, poverty, and increased social problems. This study aims to explore the impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the socio-economic status of the workforce in Jordan, the effectiveness of government's measures, and the lessons learned as perceived by stakeholders. A random sample of 541 workers was drawn from the north, middle, and south of Jordan using the quantitative and qualitative methods of questionnaire (n=520) and interview (n=21). The results revealed that the pandemic has severely affected the social and economic status and that the effectiveness of the government's reaction to the pandemic was moderate. The study concludes with the lesson learned, suggested solutions, implications, and recommendations for future research.

Introduction

The rapid spread of COVID-19 (aka Coronavirus) since the end of 2019 has had serious economic, social, and political repercussions worldwide. The global economy has been seriously affected (Sahir, Saputra, & Sari, 2021). The Virus, declared a pandemic in March 2020, has managed to put the world in a trance and become a threat to humanity. The rapidly-spreading virus killed many (Subathra, Krishnakumari, & Yuvaraj, 2021), and the death toll increased dramatically as it raged out of control. Many countries around the globe fell prey to social problems and a major economic recession (Michelle, 2020), which affected both workforce mobility and trade flows (Raouf, Elsabbagh, & Wiebelt, 2020).

As soon as the World Health Organization (WHO) declared the virus a global pandemic in March 2020, governments around the world began enforcing preventive and control measures to mitigate the negative effects of the pandemic. The pandemic has brought about uncertainty, new norms of behavior, and a quest for solutions for an emerging crisis that constitutes a challenge to decision-makers at all levels (Al-Tammemi, 2020).

The literature on COVID-19 is rather limited, and the research is still ongoing (Arshad, 2020). Previous research is strongly connected to this research since both examine the impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the social and economic domains. The literature reports significant challenges and negative effects on the economy, increase in unemployment rates, decrease in income, uncertainty in the future, poor government support, and no clear recovery strategies. Subathra, Krishnakumari, and Yuvaraj (2021) argue that the Pandemic transformed the way people work, shop, and communicate, as they were forced to stay in and many started working from home. Priorities seemed to shift from spending on luxuries to buying food, medical supplies, disinfectants and antiseptics. Restrictions were put into effect, and self-isolation, lockdowns, social distancing, limited mobility and travel, and reduced workforce and lay-offs across sectors ensued (International Monetary Funds (IMF), 2020).

Jordan Center for Strategic Studies (JCSS, 2020) reported that the pandemic has hit the world so hard that unprecedented economic, social, health, and educational damage was incurred. The world has come together to combat the pandemic, as the spread in one country affected the rest of the world. Countries came together in their quest to combat the pandemic whose impact was evident on all aspects of life.

Jordan was no different from the rest of the world, as its workforce faced unprecedented problems with no foreseen end. In fact, the economic difficulties brought about by the pandemic appear to be the most damaging in decades (JCSS, 2020, p.36), as the impact of the Virus on Jordan's tourism sector, for example, is said to be more damaging than that of the Gulf War (Al-Nsour, 2021).

Employment in various sectors has been heavily affected by the Pandemic. For example, the tourism sector, the second-largest employer in Jordan, recorded a sharp fall in the number of foreign tourists and, consequently, seasonal employees in the tourism sector were hit hard by the Pandemic. Similarly, dwindling demand for manufacturing, construction, transportation, trade services, and agriculture sectors has also contributed to the decline in employment (Raouf, Elsabbagh, & Wiebelt, 2020).

According to the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2020), the pandemic has exposed individual, societal, and sectorial vulnerabilities across the globe, which alerted to an immediate need for pervasive economic and social remedial measures. The pandemic has drawn attention to the need for solidarity, cooperation, and responsibility by all. Social and economic enterprises, for instance, are needed to share their business models to redesign, implement, and support post-crisis economies and communities.

The COVID-19 Pandemic is a crisis indeed, one which constitutes an undesired, extraordinary, unexpected, and time-bound process with uncertain outcomes (Glaesser, 2006). As such, the pandemic may manifest itself in one of the following:

1. immediate with no or very little advance warning, so much so that organizations are not able to formulate mitigation strategies or prepare contingency plans before the crisis;
2. emerging whose progress is slower and may be stopped or slowed down by actions on the part of the organization; and
3. sustained which may last for months or even years (Ritchie 2009).

Fink (1986, p.15) maintains that crisis management is the "art of removing much of the risk and uncertainty to allow you to achieve more control over your destiny". The crisis events are usually unpredictable, but they are not always unexpected and, hence, different organizational responses should be organized and well-coordinated for proper crisis management (Efficiency Unit, 2009). Ritchie (2009) put forth the following stages of crisis management:

1. planning and preparation of activities before a crisis, which comprises data collection through monitoring the external and internal environment for crisis signals;
2. crisis or disaster response and containment, which comprises putting plans and formulating strategies to manage the crisis; and
3. redesign of crises management strategies to bridge gaps.

These stages may be developed by designing a detailed module of systematic procedures to overcome a crisis. Global economic growth projections for 2020 have been decreased, reflecting a dramatic worldwide economic decline which brought about restrictive pandemic-related measures. Locally, the Jordanian government has taken strict precautionary measures since the advent of the crisis to limit the spread of the Coronavirus. Lockdowns, social distancing, and mandatory mask requirements were enforced to contain the outbreak.

Like other countries around the world, Jordan has suffered massive economic and social difficulties across sectors. Transportation and supply chains were affected by the restrictions caused by the successive lockdowns, and the workforce, especially that in the private and informal (daily-wage) sectors, were the most affected.

Problem, Purpose, and Questions of the Study

The COVID-19 Pandemic hit at a time when the Jordanian economy has already been suffering from deterioration and general weakness brought about by recurring economic and financial crises, which has affected economic and social institutions at all levels. The repercussions of the restrictive measures (e.g., curfews, closures) affected small and large businesses alike, causing closures, financial loss, unemployment, and most importantly, a massive social dilemma.

Different preventive and control measures (e.g., movement restrictions, curfews, closures, defense orders) have been enforced around the world to combat the spread of the virus (UNDP, 2020). Jordan implemented a series of preventive and control measures to mitigate the negative effects of the virus. Domestically, the government has taken measures to deliver food and basic supplies not only to Jordanians at their homes but also to refugees in camps across Jordan (Alzghol, 2020). The government further provided Internet connectivity to facilitate online education for all and paid living expenses for less-privileged families. Internationally, the government banned in-bound travel of non-Jordanian from several countries (e.g., China, Iran, United Kingdom, Italy), which compounded the pressure on the economy and society alike (Ministry of Health (MoH), 2020).

This study aims to explore the impact of the pandemic on the economic and social status of the Jordanian workforce. The study further aims to explore the effectiveness, or lack thereof, of workforce-related government measures and stakeholders' perspectives about the lessons learned from the Pandemic and potential solutions to address similar future crises. More specifically, the study attempts to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio-economic status of the Jordanian workforce during the COVID-19 Pandemic?
2. What are respondents' perspectives about the effectiveness of governmental measures during the pandemic?
3. Are there any statistically significant differences (at $\alpha=0.05$) in the socio-economic status of the Jordanian workforce during the Covid-19 Pandemic, which can be attributed to the demographic variables of gender, workplace, work status, income, and sector?
4. Are there any statistically significant differences (at $\alpha=0.05$) in the government procedures, which can be attributed to the demographic variables of gender, workplace, work status, income, and sector?
5. What are the lessons learned from the pandemic as perceived by various stakeholders?

6. What are the potential solutions for the pandemic and similar future crises as perceived by stakeholders?

Method and Procedures

This research was conducted during the defense orders and lockdowns at the peak of the COVID-19 Pandemic. The target population comprised the Jordanian workforce, which amounted to 2.6 million workers (World Bank, 2020; 2021), in the private and public sectors. Geographically, Jordan is divided into three regions (viz., North, Middle, and South) which encompass twelve governorates (viz., Irbid, Amman, Ajloun, Mafraq, Zarka, Madaba, Karak, Tafeleh, Maan, Aqaba, Jerash, and Balqa). The research was carried out in all three regions, yet only four governorates were randomly selected to draw the sample of the research, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Sample Demographics and Distribution

Variable	Category	n	%
Workplace (by Region)	North	252	48.09
	Middle	166	31.68
	South	106	20.23
Gender	Male	249	47.52
	Female	275	52.48
Work Status	Employed	332	63.36
	Temporarily unemployed	118	22.52
	Unemployed	74	14.12
Sector	Trade	130	24.81
	Industry	111	21.18
	Services	283	54.01
Income	Less than 260 JD	210	40.08
	JD 260-<JD500	205	39.12
	JD 500-<JD700	63	12.02
	>JD700	46	8.78
Total		524	100

Based on an extensive review of related literature and the collective experience of the researchers, a 35-item questionnaire was designed to collect the data for this study. The questionnaire consists of two parts: the first covers the social and economic status (13 and 7 items, respectively) whereas the second addresses the impact of government measures for alleviating the negative impact on the workforce (17 items).

In the first part of the questionnaire, the respondents were asked to rate their perceptions on a five-point Likert Scale from *strongly disagree* to *strongly agree*. In the second part, they were asked to rate their perceptions of the effectiveness of government Pandemic-related measures on a three-point Likert Scale from *low effectiveness* to *high effectiveness*.

The COVID-19 Pandemic forced workers to accept short-term contracts; during the COVID-19 Pandemic, the workforce lost faith in economic security due to unstable government decisions; and the COVID-19 Pandemic has increased physical and psychological violence within families. Similarly, governmental procedures have increased unemployment, the COVID-19 Pandemic has caused many of the workers abroad to return to Jordan, which placed more pressure on the local workforce, and the COVID-19 Pandemic has exposed problems in social values (e.g., excessive buying; hoarding) are examples of the items in the second part of the questionnaire.

For the second part of the study, which focuses on the lessons learned and solutions proposed for future crises, the researchers designed a seven-question schedule. The schedule was used to interview expert stakeholders in the three regions.

The validity of the questionnaire and interview schedule was established by a jury of experts in business, career education, and measurement and evaluation. Their feedback (viz. modifying, deleting, and adding items) was used to produce the final versions of the instruments.

Furthermore, the reliability of the questionnaire was established through piloting it on 50 workers who were excluded from the sample of the research. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the social and economic status amounted to 0.858 whereas that for government measures amounted to 0.911, both of which are deemed appropriate for the purpose of the current research (Cronbach & Shavelson, 2004).

The questionnaire was distributed both hand-to-hand and electronically. The researchers made sure that the participants understood the purpose of the research, probing the real socio-economic status of the Jordanian workforce during the COVID-19 Pandemic. The participants' consent to take part in the study was obtained after assuring them that the data will be confidentially used for the purposes of the current research.

One thousand and two hundred copies of the questionnaire were distributed, of which 524 were returned (43 percent) and subjected to the analysis. Interviews were conducted with 21 expert stakeholders whose responses were recorded, transcribed, and analyzed to probe the lessons learned and suggestions for preparedness for future crises.

Frequencies and percentages, means and standard deviations, and five-way ANOVA and MANOVA were used in the analysis of the data, using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS).

A three-point Likert scale (viz., high, moderate, and low) was used to elicit the respondents' perspectives about the socio-economic impact of COVID-19 and the effectiveness of the relevant government procedures during the pandemic. The levels of the scale of the socio-economic effect of the COVID_19 Pandemic were set at the following ranges:

- Low: less than 2.33
- Moderate: 2.34-3.66
- High: 3.67-5.00

Similarly, the three levels of the scale used for gauging the effectiveness of government measures were set as follows:

- Low: less than 1.66
- Moderate: 1.67-2.33
- High: 2.34-3.00

Results of the Study

The First Research Question

To answer the first research question, which seeks to identify the socio-economic status of the Jordanian workforce during the COVID-19 Pandemic, means and standard deviation for each of the two domains and for each item of each domain were calculated; as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Means and Standard Deviations of the Economic and Social Domains

Rank	Domain	Mean	SD	Level of Agreement
1	Economic Status	4.23	0.48	High
2	Social Status	3.96	0.48	High
Overall		4.06	0.42	High

Maximum mean score=5

Table shows that both domains achieved high level of agreement, with a higher mean for the economic status. The overall mean score for the two domains amounted to 4.06, which also manifested a high degree of agreement. Table 3 shows the means and Standard Deviations of the economic status of the Jordanian workforce.

Table 3. Means and Standard Deviations of the Economic Status Domain

Rank	Item Number	Domain	Mean	SD	Level of Agreement
1	1	The COVID-19 Pandemic has brought about a lack of vacancies for unemployed youth.	4.64	0.62	High
2	3	The COVID-19 Pandemic has led to a cut in wages for those who continued work during the Pandemic.	4.47	0.71	High
3	2	The COVID-19 Pandemic has forced workers to accept short-term contracts.	4.43	0.68	High
4	5	During COVID-19 Pandemic, the workforce lost faith in economic security due to unstable government decisions.	4.25	0.89	High
5	4	The COVID-19 Pandemic has made it difficult for the workforce to purchase food and groceries.	4.01	0.95	High
6	6	The COVID-19 Pandemic has made the workforce reconsider its spending priorities.	3.98	0.97	High
7	7	During the COVID-19 Pandemic, prices of groceries increased because of high demand.	3.81	1.11	High
	Overall		4.23	0.48	High

Maximum mean score=5

Table 3 shows that Item 1, *the COVID-19 Pandemic has brought about a lack of vacancies for unemployed youth*, tops the mean scores with 4.64. On the other hand, Item 7, *during the COVID-19 Pandemic, prices of groceries increased because of high demand*, has the lowest mean score of 3.81. The overall mean score for the Economic Status of the Workforce Domain amounted to 4.23. The level of agreement for the means of the individual items and the domain overall is *high*. Table 4 below shows the means and standard deviations of the Social Status Domain.

Table 4. Means and Standard Deviations of the Social Status Domain

Rank	Item Number	Items	Mean	SD	Level of Agreement
1	7	The COVID-19 Pandemic has exposed poverty and unemployment pockets.	4.19	0.92	High

1	13	The COVID-19 Pandemic has put more pressure on the workforce in the health sector.	4.19	0.91	High
3	11	The COVID-19 Pandemic has put more pressure on the workforce in fear of getting infected.	4.09	0.94	High
4	1	During the COVID-19 Pandemic, the number of families who received humanitarian assistance has increased.	4.03	1.00	High
5	5	The COVID-19 Pandemic has changed people's dietary patterns.	4.02	0.80	High
6	9	The COVID-19 Pandemic has increased mental disorder among the workforce.	4.01	0.96	High
7	8	The COVID-19 Pandemic has exposed problems in social values (e.g., excessive buying; hoarding).	3.94	0.97	High
8	10	The COVID-19 Pandemic has caused many of the workers abroad to return to Jordan, which increased the pressure on the local workforce.	3.93	1.04	High
9	4	During the COVID-19 Pandemic, there was a notable increase in violence in the society (fighting, physical, and verbal harassment)	3.92	0.99	High
10	2	The COVID-19 Pandemic has increased physical and psychological violence within families.	3.90	1.01	High
11	3	The COVID-19 lockdown has forced family members to stay together.	3.83	1.01	High
12	12	The COVID-19 Pandemic has exhausted the front-line workforce (e.g., health professionals, police personnel).	3.80	0.93	High
13	6	The COVID-19 Pandemic has contributed to increased divorce rates.	3.67	1.07	High
Overall			3.96	0.48	High

Maximum mean score=5.

Table 4 shows that Items 7 and 13, *the COVID-19 Pandemic has exposed poverty and unemployment pockets*) and *The COVID-19 Pandemic has put more pressure on the workforce in the health sector*, top the mean scores with 4.19. whereas items 12 and 6, *the COVID-19 Pandemic has exhausted the front-line workforce (e.g., health professionals, police personnel)* and *the COVID-19 Pandemic has contributed to increased divorce rates*, have the lowest mean scores (3.80 and 3.67, respectively). The overall mean score for the Social Status of the Workforce Domain amounted to 3.96. The level of agreement for the individual items and the domain overall is high.

The Second Research Question

To answer the second research question, which addresses the respondents' perspectives about the effectiveness of the government procedures during the COVID-19 Pandemic, means and standard deviations for each item and the overall mean score of the domain were calculated, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Means and Standard Deviations of the Perspectives about the Effectiveness of Government Procedures

Rank	Item Number	Item	Mean	SD	Level of Agreement
1	1	facilitating money transfer	2.27	0.68	Moderate
2	2	spreading the national fund support	2.13	0.71	Moderate
3	6	deferring loan payment of low-income families	2.10	0.72	Moderate
4	3	combatting unemployment	2.09	0.72	Moderate
5	14	extending debt-payment deadlines	2.05	0.69	Moderate
6	7	temporarily waiving fees for low-income families	2.02	0.70	Moderate
7	8	tax exemptions for low-income families	2.01	0.71	Moderate
8	4	facilitating paid sick leaves	2.00	0.69	Moderate
9	11	encouraging banks to pump more cash into the market	1.96	0.70	Moderate
10	9	granting soft loans to support small businesses	1.96	0.67	Moderate
11	12	increasing tax exemptions for employers	1.95	0.71	Moderate
11	10	granting loans to individual business owners	1.95	0.69	Moderate
13	5	distributing food vouchers to disadvantaged families	1.94	0.69	Moderate
13	13	raising wages	1.94	0.70	Moderate
15	15	setting up compensation funds for laid-off	1.89	0.69	Moderate

Rank	Item Number	Item	Mean	SD	Level of Agreement
	Overall	workers	2.02	0.43	Moderate

Maximum mean score=3.

Table 6 Tables hows that the respondents perceptions of the government procedures in Item, *facilitating money transfer*, and 15, *setting up compensation funds for laid-off workers*, scored the highest and lowest means, 2.27 and 1.89, respectively. The overall mean for the Effectiveness of Government Procedures Domain amounted to 2.02. These and all other items fell within the *moderate* level of agreement.

The Third Research Question

To answer the third research question, which seeks potential statistically significant differences (at $\alpha = 0.05$) in the socio-economic status of the Jordanian workforce during the COVID-19 Pandemic which can be attributed to the demographic variables of gender, workplace, status, income, and sector, means and standard deviations for each item and the overall mean score of the domain were calculated, as shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Means and Standard Deviations of the Socioeconomic Status of Jordanian Workforce by Demographic Variables

Variable	Category	Mean	SD
Gender	Male	3.96	0.43
	Female	4.14	0.40
Workplace	North	4.16	0.44
	Middle	4.02	0.44
	South	3.86	0.27
Work Status	Employed	4.05	0.45
	temporarily unemployed	4.02	0.35
	Unemployed	4.12	0.40
Income	<JD 260	4.04	0.42
	JD 260-<JD500	4.06	0.42
	JD 500-<JD700	4.05	0.44
	>JD700	4.14	0.46
Sector	Trade	4.03	0.45
	Industry	3.96	0.32
	Services	4.11	0.44

Table 6 shows observed differences in the means and the standard deviations of perceived socio-economic status of the Jordanian workforce during the COVID-19 Pandemic which can be attributed to the demographic variables of gender, workplace, status, income, and sector. To determine the potential statistical significance of these differences, Five-Way Analysis of Variance was used, as shown in Table 7.

Table7. Five-Way ANOVA of the Socioeconomic Status of Jordanian Workforce by Demographic Variables

Variable	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	f	Sig.
Gender	2.322	1	2.322	14.292	0.000*
Workplace	4.538	2	2.269	13.963	0.000*
Work Status	0.075	2	0.037	0.230	0.795
Sector	0.490	3	0.163	1.005	0.390
Income	0.023	2	0.012	0.072	0.931
Error	83.353	513	0.162		
Corrected Total	93.654	523			

*statistically significant at $\alpha=0.05$

Table7 shows statistically significant differences (at $\alpha=0.05$), in the perceived overall socioeconomic status of the Jordanian workforce during the COVID-19, which can be attributed to gender, in favor of female respondents. Similarly, there are statistically significant differences, which can be attributed to workplace. To determine which means are significant, Scheffe test was used, as shown in Table.

Table8.Scheffe of the Socioeconomic Status of the Jordanian Workforce by Workplace

Workplace (by Region)	Mean	North	Middle	South
North	4.16	-	0.14*	0.30*
Middle	4.02		-	0.16*
South	3.86			-

*statistically significant at $\alpha=0.05$

Table 8 shows significant differences between workplace regions : north and middle in favor of the former ($\bar{x} = 4.16$ vs. 4.02, respectively), between north and south in favor of the former ($\bar{x} = 4.16$ vs. 3.86, respectively), and between south and middle in favor of the latter ($\bar{x} = 4.02$ vs. 3.86, respectively).

The Fourth Research Question

To answer the fourth research question, which seeks potential statistically significant differences (at $\alpha = 0.05$) in the perceived effectiveness of the government procedures during the COVID-19 Pandemic which can be attributed to the demographic variables of gender, workplace, status, income, and sector, means and standard deviations for each item and the overall mean score of the domain were calculated, as shown in Table 9.

Table 9. Means and Standard Deviations of the Effectiveness of Government Procedures by Demographic Variables

Variable	Category	Mean	SD
Gender	Male	2.08	0.40
	Female	1.96	0.45
Workplace	North	1.94	0.46
	Middle	2.02	0.45
	South	2.19	0.22
Work Status	Employed	2.02	0.43
	temporarily unemployed	2.09	0.38
Income	Unemployed	1.89	0.47
	< JD 260	2.05	0.43
	JD 260 to < JD 500	2.04	0.40
	JD 500 to < JD 700	1.92	0.44
Sector	> JD 700	1.87	0.54
	Trade	2.03	0.42
	Industry	2.19	0.31
	Services	1.94	0.46

Table 9 shows observed differences in the means and the standard deviations of perceived effectiveness of government procedures during the COVID-19 Pandemic which can be attributed to the demographic variables of gender, workplace, status, income, and sector. To determine the potential statistical significance of these differences, Five-Way Analysis of Variance was used, as shown in Table 10 below.

Table 10. Five-Way ANOVA of the Effectiveness of Government Procedures by Workplace

Variable	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	f	Sig.
Gender	0.248	1	0.248	1.463	0.227
Workplace	1.580	2	0.790	4.659	0.010*
Work Status	0.969	2	0.485	2.858	0.058
Sector	1.972	2	0.986	5.814	0.003*
Income	1.974	3	0.658	3.879	0.009*
Error	86.998	513	0.170		
Corrected Total	97.241	523			

*statistically significant at $\alpha=0.05$

Table10 shows statistically significant differences (at $\alpha=0.05$), in the perceived effectiveness of government procedures during the COVID-19 Pandemic, which can be attributed to workplace, sector, income. To determine the significance of the procedures by workplace, Scheffe test was used, as shown in Table 11.

Table 11. Scheffe of the Effectiveness of Government Procedures by Workplace

Workplace	Mean	North	Middle	South
North	1.94	-	-0.08	-0.25*
Middle	2.02		-	-0.17*
South	2.19			-

*statistically significant at $\alpha=0.05$

Table 11 shows significant differences between workplace regions : north and south in favor of the latter ($\bar{x} = 1.94$ vs. 2.19, respectively), between south and middle in favor of the former ($\bar{x} = 2.19$ vs. 2.02, respectively). To determine the significance of the procedures by sector, Scheffe test was used, as shown in Table 12.

Table 12. Scheffe of the Effectiveness of Government Procedures by Sector

Sector	Mean	Trade	Industry	Services
Trade	2.03	-	-0.17*	0.08
Industry	2.19		-	0.25*
Services	1.94			-

*statistically significant at $\alpha=0.05$

Table 12 shows significant differences between the sectors of trade and industry , in favor of the latter ($\bar{x} = 2.03$ vs. 2.19, respectively) and between the sectors of services and industry , in favor of the latter ($\bar{x} = 1.94$ vs. 2.19, respectively). To determine the significance of the procedures by income, Scheffe test was used, as shown in Table 13.

Table 13.Scheffe of the Effectiveness of Government Procedures by Income

Income	Mean	< JD260	JD260-< JD500	500-< JD700	> JD700
< JD260	2.05	-	0.01	0.13	0.18*
JD260-< JD500	2.04		-	0.12	0.17
500-< JD700	1.92			-	0.05
> JD700	1.87				-

*statistically significant at $\alpha=0.05$

Table 13 shows significant differences between the income categories of < JD260 and > JD700, in favor of the former ($\bar{x} = 2.05$ vs. 1.87, respectively).

The Fifth and Sixth Research Questions

Lessons Learned and Suggestions for Handling Future Crises

The Pandemic has affected all aspects of life, and, as it unraveled, taught us lessons never to forget. To glean some of these lessons, the researchers have initially set out to conduct 50 interviews with stakeholders from the three regions of Jordan. However, for circumstances beyond these researchers' control, only 21 interviews were conducted, recorded, and eventually analyzed to identify stakeholders' perspectives about the impact of the Pandemic on the Jordanian workforce.

The analysis of the interview data revealed that the participants almost unanimously reported that the impact of the Pandemic was so immense that it raged out of the control not only of the Jordanian workforce but also of the government itself. The respondents seem to see the Pandemic as an international crisis whose impact encompasses all and needs serious collaborative efforts to mitigate. They seemed aware of the catastrophic repercussions of closures, defense orders, and curfews on the economy which has been forced into an unprecedented recession. They reported on dramatic pay-cuts and workers' having to compromise to survive through the Pandemic with soaring unemployment rates among young men and women alike.

In terms of social problems, the interviewees reported escalation in domestic violence, divorce rates, and substance abuse and a surge in the number of families needing urgent support. The stakeholders also pointed out problems between home and property owners and tenants. On the brighter side, the interviewees reported a heartening increase in solidarity and collaboration within the community and stronger familial and social ties brought about by the Pandemic.

The stakeholders reported their satisfaction with the effectiveness of government health-related decisions, but nine were satisfied with the government economy-related decisions throughout the Pandemic. The interviewees reported believing that no sector was untouched by the Pandemic, as it impacted small businesses in tourism, trade, agriculture, and the industry in which most of the Jordanian workforce is concentrated.

When asked to put forth potential solutions to mitigate the impact of unexpected conditions similar to those experienced during the Pandemic, almost all suggested establishing and maintaining fund reserves to guard for and help the workforce overcome similar future crises. Respondents also addressed issues related to revising the Jordanian labor laws, setting up contingency plans, encouraging small businesses working from home, focusing on women entrepreneurs, and encouraging the participation of young men and women in agricultural projects.

Covid-19 has exposed the world to an unprecedented conditions and instigated novel experiences which may enable governments and citizens alike to better respond to future challenges. Governments have learned the hard way how to be prepared on all fronts, be it in the health, education, economic, social, or political sectors. COVID-19 has uncovered lethal flaws in both the educational and health systems in Jordan and probably less serious flaws in the social and economic arenas.

In response to this and any potential future crises, the government need design, develop, implement, and evaluate a country-wide strategic plan for all sectors. For example, in terms of the health sector, not only should the quality of the infrastructure, capacity, and services provided by the existing hospitals and medical centers be improved but new ones should also be built to cater for the growing population and the rising need for quality health care. Moreover, the government, with the help of civil society and non-governmental organizations, should work on the design and provision of awareness and capacity-building campaigns for better and timely response to similar future crises. Furthermore, front-line personal (e.g., health professionals, civil defense forces) should be provided with state-of-the-art training and assistive technologies to handle emergent crises.

The economy has been hit hard by the Pandemic, and unprecedented rates of unemployment have ensued. The successive closures and defense orders have left an unprecedented number of people unemployed, which has brought about a decrease or loss of income which, in turn, caused families to struggle to secure their basic needs (e.g., food, fuel). One solution may be for the government to pump money into the market and enable banks

and *lending* institutions to grant low- or no-interest loans to mitigate the impact of the Pandemic. Well-planned government intervention would not only decrease the financial risks brought about by the Pandemic but also restore and strengthen trust in the government procedures.

The COVID-19 Pandemic has caused social and economic distress and negatively affected the Jordanian workforce and their living conditions. The Pandemic has also put huge pressure on the health sector and constituted a hazard, often a deadly one, to health professionals and, by extension, their families and loved ones. Other less obvious problems were weakened social values, increased violence, and increased divorce rates. The social and economic impact of COVID-19 will last long after the Pandemic is over and will require significant and direct interventions, clear strategies, and effective policies to enable stakeholder to recover from the its devastating repercussions.

Discussion and Conclusions

The perceived overall socio-economic status of the workforce during the COVID-19 Pandemic was near unanimous, as the respondents showed high levels of agreement that the COVID-19 Pandemic has decreased job opportunities and increased unemployment among youth. This is consistent with statistics by government and non-government organizations which indicate that the unemployment rate exceeded 45% in youth, which potentially affects them and their families alike.

The Pandemic is believed to have a lesser impact on the government employees, compared to those who in the small business sector. The Pandemic has also had a serious impact on those who stayed in their respective jobs, as they had to work the same amount of time but to endure pay cuts, which sometimes exceeded 50 percent of their wages before the Pandemic.

Despite near heroic efforts by the Jordanian government to mitigate the negative impact of the Pandemic, the majority of the workforce lost faith in economic security because of unstable government decisions (Jordan Economic and Social Council (JESC), 2020). Like in other countries around the world, the Pandemic has not only limited people's ability to make purchases (except for basic living requirements) for lack of cash and increased prices but also forced them to reorder their priorities to adjust to the hardships brought about by the Pandemic (Benfadel, 2020).

The limited expenditure by the Jordanian public and the ensuing decrease in cash flow have resulted in decreased demand for merchandise, which has lessened demand for goods and services available on the market. More importantly, curfews, lockdowns, travel restrictions, and unemployment have brought about changes in the customer behavior and spending habits not only in Jordan but all over the globe (Azize, Othman, & Sadiq, 2020).

The current findings show that fear, stress, and mental health issues are the most serious facets of impact of the Pandemic. In terms of the social status of the workforce in Jordan, the impact was obvious and disheartening. Even before the advent of the pandemic, Jordan has had one of the highest dependency ratios in the world (about 61 percent), which has rocketed as the the outbreak of the COVID-19 Pandemic compounded poverty pockets and unemployment ratios. The World Bank estimated the Jordanian economy to have contracted by 1.6 percent in 2020, with unemployment rising to 24.7 percent in the fourth quarter of 2020, and youth unemployment rates reaching an unprecedented 50 percent (World Bank, 2020).

The Pandemic has put more pressure on the workforce, who continued working, not only to support their families but also not to get infected by the Virus, because the more workers infected, the higher the unemployment and dependency ratios. The current results revealed that the pandemic has increased the number of families who receive humanitarian assistance and the number of people who seek psychological and mental health support.

The economic status has had an impact on the social status of the workforce. The Pandemic has brought about new dietary patterns, weakened social values, and increased physical and verbal violence. Moreover, the ensuing lockdowns forced family members to stay together which often flared conflicts within the family.

The results further revealed that the Pandemic has contributed to increasing divorce rates in the Jordanian society. This can be readily explained in terms of increased unemployment rates which lowered one's income and limited one's ability to meet the demands of his/her family (Atkenson, 2020). This may be even worse for Jordan whose economy has been in crisis for years before the Pandemic.

In terms of government procedures during the Pandemic, the respondents reported that the facilitative procedures of money transfer from and to Jordan have helped many families to overcome some of the hardships brought about by the Pandemic. Many Jordanians work abroad, mainly in Arabian Gulf countries, and send money to their families or invest in in certain ventures, which contributed to the alleviation of some of the pressure of the Pandemic.

The Jordanian government has also established a national fund to provide monetary assistance to the people who lost their businesses and/or jobs during the Pandemic. Among the other procedures, whose effectiveness was moderately agreed upon by the respondents, are deferring loans for low-income families, combatting unemployment, extending debt-payment deadlines, holding fees, tax exemption, paid sickness leave, and pumping cash into the market. The government has also granted soft loans to support small businesses,

increased tax exemptions for employers, granting loans to small business owners, and distributed food vouchers to disadvantaged families.

The perceptions of the impact of government procedures were affected by the respondents' workplace, sector, and income. In terms of the workplace, the stakeholders in the southern region perceived the government procedures as less effective than those in other regions of Jordan, probably because of the prevalence of poverty pockets, unemployment, and relatively low-incomes. Similarly, the results show that the services sector was the most impacted of the three (trade, industry, services) by the Pandemic, probably because the services sector was stagnant during the crisis. Furthermore, respondents whose is JD 260 or less were the most impacted in the country.

This current study also revealed that, during the Pandemic, female workers were perceived to be impacted more than their male counterparts, probably because women tend to either have their own small businesses or work in the private sector. As alluded to previously, the majority of government positions are occupied by men whose pay was affected neither closures nor lay-offs. one had been laid off because of the novel situation.

Female respondents perceived government procedures as less effective than did their male counterparts. This may be attributed to the latter's ability to seek opportunities for generating extra income, as it is generally harder for their female counterparts to seek income-generating opportunities for considerations relating to motherhood, parenting, and cultural norms.

Furthermore, the northern region of Jordan (viz., Irbid, Ajloun, Mafrq, and Jerash) was perceived as the most impacted by curfew, lockdowns and closures, probably because a high percentage of the population of this region are either workers or owners of small businesses which were hard hit from the onset of the Pandemic. The effectiveness of government procedures was perceived high by respondents from the southern region (viz., Karak, Maan, Aqaba, and Tafelah), which may be attributed to the influx of financial support received by the people of the region. Finally, the perceived effectiveness of government procedures by respondents from the middle region (viz., Amman, Madaba, Zarka, and Balqa) manifested with a moderate level of agreement, probably because the population is more affluent than that of the other two regions.

Respondents from the northern region perceived government procedures less effective than did their counterparts from the other two regions, probably due to the rate of unemployment which amounted to 25 percent among males and double that among females just before the outbreak of the Pandemic. Unemployed respondents seemed to doubt the effectiveness government procedures, compared to those employed or temporarily unemployed. Similarly, respondents who more than JD 700 a month perceived the government procedures less effective than their lower-income counterparts, probably because they either did not receive financial government support or what they received was inadequate. Finally, respondents from the services sector rated the governmental procedures as less effective than those from the trade and industry sectors, probably because they were the more affected by the restrictions brought about by the Pandemic that their counterparts from the other two sectors.

Limitations of the Study

This research was conducted during the peak of the COVID-19 Pandemic when defense orders and lockdowns were in effect. The researchers found it difficult to define the population of the research partly because of the restrictions brought about by the lockdown, which has limited the researchers' mobility and ability to physically distribute and collect the questionnaire. The scope of the research, the socio-economic impact of the Pandemic on the Jordanian workforce, which encompasses every member of the Jordanian society has also contributed to the difficulty of defining the population of the research. To partly overcome this difficulty, another batch of questionnaires was distributed electronically through e-mail, Twitter, Facebook, and MSN Messenger. Nevertheless, the response rate to the questionnaire was relatively lower: 25 percent compared to a 55 percent response rate for the hand-to hand-batch.

Another of the limitations of the study may pertain to collecting the data from only three out of twelve governorates in Jordan. However, to enhance the generalizability of the findings, snowballing was used to enable the researchers to cover a diverse segment of the workforce in those governorates. A further limitation may derive from the fact that only a questionnaire was used for data collection. Albeit valid and reliable, the questionnaire may have limited the respondents' input, which another instrument (e.g., interview, focus group) would have alleviated.

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